

EFFECTS OF INTRODUCING CONSTITUTION OF INDIA, HUMAN RIGHTS AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE TO THE UNDERGRADUATE PROGRAMME STUDENTS IN INDIAN UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract:

Education is a powerful means of influencing people and changing their attitudes. It does not merely impart knowledge in the classroom but also sensitizes students, awakens their conscience, and encourages them to live up to those ideals. The introduction of these above subjects are foundation Courses, aims to impart to the undergraduate students of India a general idea of the principal aspects of human rights and duties, awareness of environmental issues and Indian Constitution in a broad sweep. Human rights were born along with mankind but in the changing national and international context as a result of globalization, there has been a serious threat to human rights. One of the ways by which this threat could be met, is by bringing human rights education at all levels of education. The main goal of teaching Environmental sciences is that no citizen should be ignorant of environment issues. The Constitution of India is the sovereign law of India. It protects the rights of all the citizens and serves as the framework for good governance. Today's students are tomorrow's leaders. It is the responsibility of the teaching community to educate students about the Constitution and make them informed citizens. In this paper some constraints of this subject is also highlighted. If these subjects are made compulsory in universities, they should be able to expect decent employment after graduation. Appropriate teaching methods are required for teachers & students. Training of teachers should be done through periodic workshops with interdisciplinary participation could be rewarding. Holding periodic workshops of those engaged in these fields in universities, and at the regional and national level could go a long way in building capacities and expertise. This paper speaks about the advantage and benefit to the student, constraint of teaching and learning as well as disadvantages of introducing this subject to all degree students. This paper also stress on the competency of the faculties to teach the subject.

Index Terms: Attitudes, Human Rights, Globalization, Sovereign Law & Interdisciplinary

Introduction:

A course for a degree is focused on providing study of academics. The curriculum of a degree stresses more on theoretical overview of several subjects and a particular subject that a candidate is interested in, career wise and academic wise. This education is the process of instruction aimed at the all round development of individuals, providing the necessary tools and knowledge to understand and participate in day to day activities of today's world. Education expands ones vision and outlook, provokes the spirit of healthy competition and a desire to advance for the achievements of their consciousness regenerating truth, and thereby capability to fight ignorance, injustice, corruption, violence, disparity and communalism, the greatest hazards to the progress of the nation.

Along with regular subjects UGC, Bar Council of India and Supreme Court has also made three subjects compulsory for undergraduate courses of all branches of Higher Education in India. These are called foundation Courses, aims to impart to the undergraduate students a general idea of the principal aspects of human rights and duties, The importance of environmental science and environmental studies an Constitution of India in a broad sweep.

Human Rights and Duties:

The concept of human rights is not a new phenomenon; it was prevailing from Vedic period. Human rights are inherent rights, which are given by the nature itself to a human being. The development of the human rights took place systematically after the II world war. Human rights were born along with mankind. However, over the years, human rights concept as such has gone through a set of transformation. Needless to say, in the present times, human rights have become more and more relevant. There are various dimensions of human rights out of which only civil and political rights were focused upon for a long time. However, today the economic, social and cultural rights are also being given prominence. As such the human rights in the broader sense have paved the way to new laws, charters and covenants. Notwithstanding this, in the changing national and international context as a result of globalization, there has been a serious threat to human rights. One of the ways by which this threat could be met, is by bringing human rights education at all levels of education.

Human rights are standards that allow all people to live with dignity, freedom, equality, justice, and peace. Every person has these rights simply because they are human beings. They are guaranteed to everyone without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth, or other status. Human rights are essential to the full development of individuals and communities.

Human rights reflect the minimum standards necessary for people to live with dignity. Human rights give people the freedom to choose how they live, how they express themselves, and what kind of government they want to support, among many other things. Human rights also guarantee people the means necessary to satisfy their basic needs, such as food, housing, and education, so they can take full advantage of all opportunities. Finally, by guaranteeing life, liberty, equality, and security, human rights protect people against abuse by those who are more powerful.

Environmental Studies:

There are so many environmental activist filed a public interest litigation and individual petition in the Supreme Court of India to protect the Environment. On request of these people the Supreme Court of India played active role in introducing the environmental studies as a mandatory paper to all the UG students of Indian Universities through the University Grant Commission to make them to understand the importance of protecting the environment from exploitation.

The importance of environmental science and environmental studies cannot be disputed. The need for sustainable development is a key to the future of mankind. Continuing problems of pollution, loss of forest, solid and liquid waste disposal (Domestic and Bio-Medical Waste) degradation of environment, issues like economic productivity and national security, Global warming, the depletion of ozone layer and loss of biodiversity have made everyone aware of environmental issues.

Constitution of India:

Constitution of India is a fundamental law of the land with 448 articles and 25 parts with 12 schedules. Indian constitution is written and one of the lengthiest

constitution in the world. In India constitution is sovereign and ultimate; all other laws are subordinate to the constitution. This clearly explains the political system of the nation and rights and duties of the governed.

Discussion:

The value of a nation is ascertained on the grounds of quality and character of its citizens. Education plays a very crucial role in shaping the character and quality of people. This is a generally accepted fact.

There is a great need of promoting the fundamental rights and human rights in the modern days. For the public good it's necessary of marshalling the rights and duties of individual in society. With all these views and objectives the Supreme Court of India, UGC, National Human Rights Commission and other individual activist joined together and gave their suggestion to introduce the constitution of India, Human rights and environmental studies as compulsory paper for the student of undergraduate programme in Indian universities.

Advantages:

Introduction of above mentioned three subjects as its own advantage to the nation and citizen.

- ✓ It Promote the human dignity
- ✓ Promote the awareness of rights and suggest the mechanism to safeguard their rights.
- ✓ It also contributes to build the discipline in the society.
- ✓ By knowing their rights they can defend themselves.
- ✓ The exploitation of environment will reduce.
- ✓ Sustainable development will be possible.
- ✓ It makes the people to understand the importance of protecting the environment.

Benefits to the Students:

The study of their own country constitution and studying the importance environment as well as understanding their own human rights help the students to concentrate on their day to day discipline. It also gives the knowledge and strength to face the society and people. It also makes the student to understand the relationship between individual and group. Students will learn respect the other people's rights in their maturity. It increases the human values as well as intellectual and analytical skill with the students. By studying all these subjects in their degree level they will learn to solve the dispute in a non-violent way.

Constrain of the Study:

The effective study of Constitution of India, Human Rights and Environmental Studies is not possible in one or two semester with 75 to 100 hours of duration. The effective study consumes long duration to make them to understand the concept thoroughly. Moreover they will not be having any practical knowledge like court visit, moot court, mock trials and other like law students. So here the other discipline degree students may not learn all these subjects accurately with proper knowledge. This will limits their practical approaches in a society and restrict them from defending themselves.

To speak in other side of limitation these subjects is followed with legal language and which may be very difficult to make the student to follow this. The teachers also should be qualified with legal knowledge to teach the subject effectively. Most of the educational institution will not be hiring the professional expert to teach these subjects,

they will manage the subject in such a way to make the student to pass in the subject rather than making him to understand the subject an its applicability in life.

Disadvantages:

These subjects provide lot of benefits to the learner as well as to the society. But still it has some followed disadvantages also. When student will know their human rights it might make them to raise the voice against the government now and then. Moreover the students may not be having complete knowledge about the rights and which promote them for wrong interpretation of the rights. There is a chance of using the rights negatively.

Conclusion:

It is expected by every citizen of the country to know their nation's constitution as well their basic rights and about their surroundings. The Supreme court of India, UGC and NHRC have taken active role in introducing these subjects to the undergraduate programme students in Indian universities and they have succeed with it. The attempt to impart the knowledge and spread the awareness about the environment is very much necessary in this juncture. Our environment is in present really in danger and it is required to be protected by every individual. It is the responsibility of all universities and colleges to make the student to understand the importance of these subjects in their life. This paper critically analyzed with my own views to understand the advantages, disadvantages and benefits to the student. This paper also highlights on the difficulties of understanding the subjects and teaching the subjects.

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